

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 39 (2021) 61-75

EISSN 2543-5426

Quality Evaluation of Different Branded Tea Sold in Nigeria

E. N. Onyeneke

Department of Nutrition and Dietetics, Faculty of Health Sciences, Imo State University in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

E-mail address: estyninika@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this study, the proximate, mineral, anti-nutrient content and sensory evaluation of the tea brands sold in Nigeria were evaluated. Four brands including Lipton tea (LPT), Anti Malaria Tea (AMT), Green Tea (GRT) and Eternal slimming tea (SLM) and lemon grass tea (LEM) as control were studied. The official methods of Analysis of Association of Analytical Chemists were adopted for the analysis. Results for proximate showed that GRT showed significant difference ($P > 0.05$) Moisture content (5.99 %) while SLM had significant low value $p \leq 0.05$ (4.85 %) compared to LEM (control) (5.12). The Protein content of the tea samples was discovered in traces having SLM as the highest (0.46 %). The crude fat as ether extract of the samples ranged between LPT (3.18) as the highest (3.18 %). SLM appeared to have high (6.08) value in Ash and GRT lowest value. LEM (control) had a high (88.58 %) value in Carbohydrate compared to the other tea brands with LPT as the lowest (86.03 %) value. The results of the mineral analysis showed that LEM has the highest (28.31 mg/kg, 85.96 mg/kg and 18.31 mg/kg) for calcium and potassium content respectively SLM had the highest (7.35 mg/kg) value for Magnesium. Antinutrient results showed that all teas brands had traces of alkaloid at various values ranging from GRT (0.15 mg/kg) to SLM (0.01 mg/kg). Phytate and oxalate was not detected at all in GRT and was discovered in traces the other tea brands. The average taste scores of tea samples ranged from 6.60-5.30 with highest (6.75) taste scores assigned to sample LPT while lowest (4.95) taste scores were observed in sample AMT. The four tea brands evaluated in this study are nutritionally valuable, including the natural extract of lemon grass which contains zinc, which helps boost the immune system and acts as an antioxidant that protects the body. The content of this tea brands and lemon grass are also safe.

Keywords: Anti-nutrients, Essential metals, Health, Proximate, Sensory, Slim tea, *Camellia*, *Cymbopogon citratus*

1. INTRODUCTION

The drinking of tea begun in China centuries ago, and has over the years become an inseparable part of most cultures worldwide. Tea is currently the most widely consumed beverage in the world (Schmidt *et al.*, 2005) and therefore ranks as an important world food product. About one tenth of the world production volume of tea is supplied by Kenya which is Africa's largest producer of tea (International Tea Committee, 1998).

Tea is generally consumed for its attractive aroma and taste as well as the unique place it holds in the culture of many societies. In recent times, there is renewed interest in tea because of growing consumer awareness of health benefits derived from tea consumption (McKay and Blumberg, 2002).

Tea therefore belongs to a rapidly expanding market of 'wellness beverages' (Byun and Han, 2004). By definition, tea is an infusion of the leaves or other parts of the evergreen tea plant (*Camellia* sp). Teas have been traditionally categorized into green, oolong and black teas according to the processing conditions employed during manufacturing (Kirk and Sawyer, 1997). In recent times, however, a fourth category, called herb teas, is gaining increasing popularity among consumers. Unlike traditional teas, herb teas are prepared from plants other than *Camellia* (Bender, 2003).

Tea preparation follows a simple procedure. Hot water (70 °C to 100 °C) is poured over the plant part(s) in a container and allowed to steep for a few minutes (usually 1 – 5 min) after which the plant material, usually contained in a bag, is removed from the container. The temperature of the water used and the duration of steeping affect the 'strength' of the tea. Tea is drunk hot, warm or iced.

In some cases milk and/or a sweetener such as honey or sucrose may be added before drinking (Hakim *et al.*, 2000). According to Abbey and Timpo (2000), indigenous herbs are in general heavily under-exploited in spite of their huge dietary potential.

It is therefore imperative to explore the potential of indigenous plant materials in the development of new herb teas. Three examples of indigenous plants discussed in this thesis are *Cymbopogon citratus* (Lemon grass) (Abbey and Timpo 2000).

Lemon grass has been a preferred component of many cuisines for centuries because of its excellent aromatic properties. Infusion of lemon grass leaf gives an aromatic drink with a characteristic lemon flavour (Figueirinha *et al.*, 2008). Teas are now being produced from different herbs and roots, some which are nutritionally not fit for consumption and contain some chemical that cause harm to the health if consumed.

The broad objective of this study is to comparatively assess the nutrient, the health benefits and organoleptic acceptance of various company teas produced using lemon grass herbal tea as standard. The specific objectives of the study are to: (1) determine the proximate composition of some selected tea brands, (2) determine the mineral content of some selected tea brands, (3) assess the anti-nutrient content of the tea brands and (4) assess the sensory evaluation of the tea brands.

The study is very important because it will help consumers to know the best tea to take, to the relevance to their health benefit. It will also help the government with necessary nutrition information on imported and marketed tea brands in the country and also be useful to health practioners like Nutritionist, Dietitians and even Medical Doctors in the treatment of diseases.

2. METHODOLOGY

2. 1. Sample collection

Fresh lemon grass was harvested from Imo State Polytechnic Farm Umuagwo - Ohaji in Imo State, Nigeria. It was harvested at about ten (10) cm from the tip of the leaves. All wilting and visibly diseased plant materials were removed. The samples were identified at the Department of Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture in Imo State University Imo State, Nigeria, other tea brands would be purchased from everyday supermarkets and tea marketing dealers in Owerri, Imo State. These brands include Lipton tea, Anti Malaria Tea, Green Tea and Eternal slimming tea.

2. 2. Sample preparation and storage

Figure 1. Picture of *Cymbopogon citratus*

Figure 2. Picture of Tea Samples

The plant materials (Figure 1) were carefully inspected and all foreign materials removed. The lemon grass samples would be gently rinsed in tap water. Lemon grass leaves would be cut into about three cm pieces using a stainless-steel kitchen knife. The samples were spread thinly on paper and dried in a solar drier for five days at a peak temperature of 62 °C. After drying the sample, it would be milled using an electric Binatone Blender (China, Model BLG401). The milled material was sieved through an Aluminum sieve (2 mm). Part of the sieved sample and samples of other tea brands would be stored in air tight glass bottles with tight lids and labeled.

2. 3. Proximate composition determination

The standard method of the AOAC (2000) used for the analysis of the proximate composition of the samples.

2. 3. 1. Moisture content

The standard method of the AOAC (2000) used. Two gram-portions (2g) of each grounded samples was weighed into previously weighed dry crucibles with lid. The crucibles with samples were then dried in an oven (Astel Hearson, England), at 105 °C for 24 hours. The crucibles with contents was cooled in a desiccator and weighed, then put back into the oven and the operation was repeated until a constant weight was obtained. The loss in weight obtained represented the moisture content and was calculated with the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times \frac{100}{1} \quad W_1/dx - W$$

where:

W1 = is the weight of sample before drying.

W2 = is the weight of sample after drying.

2. 3. 2. Ash content

The ash content was determined by the furnace incineration method described by AOAC (2000). Two grams (2g) portion of each sample was weighed into previously weighed and dried porcelain crucibles. The crucible and sample was placed in the muffled furnace at 550°C for 4hours (until a grey ash was left). The ash left in the crucible was cooled in a desiccator and reweighed. The ash content was calculated as

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

where:

W1 = is the weight of empty crucible

W2 = is the weight of crucible and ash.

2. 3. 3. Crude protein content

The crude protein was determined using the micro-Kjedahl technique. One gram (1g) portion of each sample was weighed into filter paper and added into the dry digestion Kjedahl

flask, followed by 0.12g of copper sulphate (CuSO₄). Two and half grams (2.5g) of sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄); and 2.50 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) were added with 3g selenium catalyst and a few anti-bumping chips. It was then heated in a flame chamber until the solution became clear (colorless). The solution was cooled to room temperature after which 80ml of distilled water was added. Then, 50 ml of 2% boric acid was placed in the receiving flask under the condenser with two drops of methyl red indicator added. The digestion flask was heated until 100 ml distillate was collected. And 10ml of the distillate was titrated with 0.649M H₂SO₄ to get pink color. The same procedure was carried out on the blank.

The amount of nitrogen was calculated.

Weight of sample = 1.0g.

Volume of H₂SO₄ required for the titration = 2.50 ml

Normality of H₂SO₄ = N

$$\text{Nitrogen \% of sample (\%N)} = \frac{\text{Titer} - \text{Blank} \times \text{Normality of acid} \times N \text{ Factor}}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Crude protein = % N × 6.25

2. 3. 4. Determination of crude fat content

The standard method of the AOAC (2000) was used. Two hundred and fifty ml (250 ml) extraction flask was washed, dried in the oven, cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The soxhlet extractor will be fitted with a reflux condenser and 3g of the dried ground sample was weighed into a filter paper, folded and transferred into a 50 mm × 10 mm extraction thimble and plugged lightly with a cotton wool. The thimble was placed in the extraction barrel and petroleum ether added until it siphoned over once in the flask directly below it. The flask was then heated and refluxed for seven hours. The thimble was then removed from the barrel and the solvent distilled off until the extraction flask was almost dry. The flask containing the fat was dried in the oven to a constant weight at 40 °C to evaporate the solvent completely, then cooled in a desiccator and weighed.

The difference in weights obtained was used to calculate as the % crude fat.

$$\% \text{ Crude fat} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{Wt \text{ of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

where:

W1 = weight of empty flask

W2 = the weight of sample with extracted fat

Wt = weight of sample

2. 3. 5. Determination of crude fiber

Twenty milliliters (20 mls) of 0.1M H₂SO₄ was poured into a 100 ml conical flask containing 2g of the defatted sample. The flask was fitted to a reflux condenser. Another 180 ml of boiling dilute sulphuric acid will be added into this flask and heat applied so that the entire liquid started boiling in 1 minute. The refluxing was continued for 30 minutes with occasional

shaking to bring down any particles attached to the side. A funnel was fitted with a filter paper (Whatman 54) and boiling water poured into the funnel and allowed to stand until the funnel was hot. The water was then drained by suction. Then the hot acid mixture was poured immediately into a shallow layer of hot water into the funnel. The suction was adjusted so that the filtration of the bulk of 200 ml (20 ml + 180 ml) was completed within 10 minutes. The residue in the filter paper was washed with boiling water until the washing was acid free. Again the residue was washed back into the original flask containing 200 ml of hot 0.3M NaOH. The liquid was boiled for 30 minutes and filtered taking the same precautions as before. Again, the residue in the filter was washed with boiling water, then with 1% HCl and finally with boiling water until the washings were free from acid. The residue was then washed with ethanol. The insoluble matter was carefully transferred into a dry and weighed crucible by means of a spatula, taking care not to dislodge any fiber from the filter paper. The crucible was dried in the oven at 70 °C for 2 hours, cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The residue was ashed into the furnace at 550 °C for 3 hours, cooled in a desiccator and weighed.

Calculation: Weight loss during ignition is the weight of the fiber

$$\% \text{fiber} = \frac{\text{Weight of fiber}}{W_2} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

where:

W₂ is the original weight of defatted sample.

2. 3. 6. Total carbohydrate

The standard method of the AOAC (2000) was used. This will be determined by the differences between the whole sample and the sum of the liquid, ash, protein, and crude fiber compositions of the sample:

$$\% \text{Carbohydrate} = 100 - [\% \text{protein} + \% \text{fat} + \% \text{Ash} + \% \text{Crude fiber}].$$

2. 4. Mineral Content Determination

The method described by Onwuka (2005) and Enyoh et al., (2019) was used in the determination of mineral content of sample. Half gram (0.5g) of the dry milled sample was weighed into a pre – acid rinsed digest tube. 10 cm³ of 6M HCl was added and heated to dryness in a water bath. The residue was dissolved in a mixture of 10 cm³ of 6M HNO₃ acid, warmed on a water bath and filtered using a Whatman filter paper into 100 cm³ calibrated flasks. The filter paper was washed with distilled water and the filtrate diluted with the distilled water and made up to the 100 cm³ mark. The digest was for the determination of calcium and potassium by the flame photometry method. The heavy metals such as Fe, Zn, and Mn were determined using the atomic absorption spectrophotometer method.

2. 5. Anti-nutrient determination

2. 5. 1. Determination of Alkaloids content of the tea samples

This was done by the alkaline precipitation gravimetric method described by AOAC (2000). Two grams (2g) of each of the sample was weighed and dispersed in 10% acetic acid

solution in ethanol to form a ratio of 1:10 (10%). The mixture was allowed to stand for 4h at 28 °C. It was later filter via Whatman No. 42 grade of filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated to one quarter of its original volume by evaporation and treated with drop wise addition of conc. aqueous NH₄OH until the alkaloid was precipitated. The alkaloid precipitated was received in a weighed filter paper, washed with 1% ammonia solution dried in the oven at 80 °C. Alkaloid content was calculated and expressed as a percentage of the weight of sample analyzed.

2. 5. 2. Determination of Phytate content of the tea sample

This was determined according to the method of AOAC (2000) and Enyoh et. al., (2020). One gram/mL of sample material was added with 0.2N HCl such that we have 3-30µg ml phytate solution, 0.5ml of extract was pipette into a test tube fitted with a ground glass stopper, then, add 1mL of solution (2), cover the tube with the stopper and fix it with a clip. The tube was heated in a boiling water bath for 30 minutes. Care was taken to ensure that the first 5 minutes that the tube remains well stopper, after cooling in ice water for 15 minutes, allow adjusting to room temperature. Once the tubes have reached room temperature, two alternative procedures may be followed.

Variant a: Mix the content of the tube and centrifuge for 30 minutes at 3000g. Transfer 1 ml of the supernant to another test tube and add 1.5ml of solution (3). Measure the absorbance at 519nm against distilled water.

Variant b: Do not centrifuge but add 2ml of solution (3) to the test tube after it has reached room temperature and mix the content. The absorbance must be measured after a defined time (0.5-1min is recommended) because the bipyridine reacts with the iron phytate and therefore the colour changes with time. The results obtained by the two alternative procedures are identical. Variant (a) is simpler to work with and has a slightly lower mean error, but variant (b) was much faster. The method has to be calibrated with the reference solutions as a substitute for the sample solution with each set of analyses.

Preparation of the calibration curve is carried out by plotting the concentrations of the reference solutions against their corresponding absorbance. Then the absorbance of the test sample is used to obtain the concentration from the calibration curve.

2. 5. 3. Determination Oxalates content of the tea samples, determination by Titration Method

This determination was carried out using method described by Singleton and Rossi (1999). This method involves three major steps digestion, precipitation and permanganate titration.

Digestion:

Two grams (2g) of sample was suspended in 190 mL of distil water in a 250 ml volumetric flask. Followed by the addition of 10 mL of 6M HCl and kept the suspension digested at 100 °C for 1hour. Then cool, and then make up to 250 ml mark before filtration.

Oxalate Precipitation:

Duplicate portions of 125 ml of the filtrate are measured into beakers and four drops of methyl red indicator added. This was followed by the addition of conc. NH₄OH solution (drop wise) until the test solution changes from salmon pink colour to a faint yellow colour (pH 4 -

4.5). Each portion is then heated to 90 °C, cooled and filtered to remove precipitate containing ferrous ion. The filtrate was again heated to 90 °C and 10ml of 5% CaCl₂ solution was added while being stirred constantly. After heating, it was cooled and left overnight at 5 °C. The solution was then centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was decanted and the precipitate completely dissolved in 10 ml of 20% (v/v) H₂SO₄ solution.

Permanganate Titration:

At this point, the total filtrate resulting from digestion of 2g of sample was made up to 300 ml. Aliquots of 125 mL of the filtrate was heated until near-boiling and then titrated against 0.05M standardized KMnCO₄ solution to a faint pink colour which persists for 30s. The calcium oxalate content was calculated using the formula.

$$\frac{T \times (Vme)(Df) \times 10^5}{(ME) \times Mf} \text{ (mg/100g)}$$

where T was the litre of KMnO₄ (ml), Vme was the volume - mass equivalent (i.e 1 cm³ of 0.05m KMnCO₄ solution is equivalent to 0.00225g anhydrous oxalic acid), Df is the dilution factor V_T/A (2.4 where V_T is the total volume of titrate (300 ml) and A is the aliquot used (125 ML), ME is the molar equivalent of KMnO₄ oxalate (KMnO₄ redox reaction) and mf is the mass of flour used.

2. 6. Sensory evaluation of tea samples

Sensory evaluation of tea samples was conducted to establish preference rating of tea for flavor, taste, color and overall acceptability. Tea samples (5g) were infused with 250 ml freshly boiled water for five minutes and then the liquid was poured into 250 ml tea tasting tea cup for quality assessment. A untrained panel of twenty judges was employed for sensory evaluation of tea samples. Before start of the evaluation a training session of 15 minutes was conducted with 20 panelists.

Figure 3. Infusion of tea samples

Figure 4. Set to be tested tea samples

Afterwards, one sample at a time was offered to each member. The sensory testing was made in the panel room with controlled temperature and relative humidity. The panel room was completely free of food/chemical odors, unnecessary sound and mixing of daylight. Judges were provided with prescribed questionnaire to record their sensory observations. The information contained on the sensory performance was indicated as 9 = extremely good; 8 = very good; 7 = moderately good; 6 = good; 5 = Neither good nor poor; 4 = poor; 3 = moderately poor; 2 = very poor; 1 = extremely poor (Larmond, 1977).

2. 7. Statistical analysis

Experimental data were assessed with one-way ANOVA using SPSS version 15.0. The p-values below or equal to 0.05 were regarded as significant. Sample means was compared to determine effect. The least significant difference was calculated at 5% level of significance of between means using tukey test (T-test) as described by Ihekoronye and Ngoddy (1985).

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Proximate composition of different tea brands

The result of proximate analysis of lipton tea, Green tea, Eternal Sliming tea, Anti-malaria tea, compared with Lemon grass are presented in the Table 1. GRT showed significant difference ($P > 0.05$) Moisture content (5.99), compared to LEM (control) (5.12), while SLM had significant low value $p \leq 0.05$ (4.85) compared to LEM (control) (5.12). The Protein content of the tea samples was discovered in traces having SLM as the highest (0.46), compared to LEM (control) as the lowest (0.19).

The crude fat as ether extract of the samples ranged between LPT (3.18) as the highest (3.18) compared to LEM as the lowest (1.07). SLM appeared to have high (6.08) value in Ash (compared to LEM (control) and GRT low value showed in Ash compared to LEM (control) (5.04). LEM (control) had a high (88.58) value in Carbohydrate compared to the other tea brands. LPT had a low (86.03) value.

Table 1. Proximate composition of different brands of tea.

Brand of tea	*Moisture %	*Protein %	*Fat %	*Ash %	*Carbohydrate
AMT	5.39 ^c ±0.02	0.23 ^b ±0.02	2.02 ^c ±0.01	4.85 ^d ±0.04	87.49 ^b ±0.02
SLM	4.85 ^e ±0.03	0.46 ^a ±0.02	2.57 ^b ±0.02	6.08 ^a ±0.03	86.03 ^d ±0.01
GRT	5.99 ^a ±0.03	0.25 ^b ±0.01	3.09 ^a ±0.02	4.20 ^e ±0.02	86.46 ^c ±0.04
LPT	5.62 ^b ±0.03	0.36 ^a ±0.03	3.18 ^a ±0.03	5.93 ^b ±0.04	84.89 ^e ±0.01
LEM (control)	5.12 ^d ±0.02	0.19 ^b ±0.01	1.07 ^d ±0.02	5.04 ^c ±0.02	88.58 ^a ±0.0
LSD (p=0.05)	0.02898	0.02408	0.02258	0.03592	0.02324

(±) standard deviation, *mean of duplicate analysis, mean scores with difference superscript letter across they are significantly different.

Key:

AMT = anti-malaria tea

SLM = slimming tea

GRT =green tea

LPT = Lipton tea

LEM = lemongrass tea

3. 2. Mineral composition of different tea brands

The results of the mineral analysis are presented in table 2 LEM (control) has the highest (28.31) calcium content compared to the other tea brands. SLM had the highest (7.35) value for Magnesium compared to LEM (control) (2.02) which had the lowest value. LEM (control) had the highest value (85.96) for potassium, when compared to other tea products, having AMT as the lowest (50.24) value, when compared to other tea brands; LEM (control) (18.31) had the highest value for Zinc, having SLM (5.10) as the lowest value. Other heavy metals compared with lemon grass and other tea brands, revealed to be below detectable limit (bdl).

Table 2. Mineral composition of different brands of tea.

Tea brands	Ca	Mg	K	Zn	Pb	Ni	Cd
AMT	6.46 ^d ±0.1	6.42 ^b ±0.05	50.24 ^e ±0.05	7.39 ^d ±0.02	Bdl	Bdl	Bdl
SLM	7.24 ^c ±0.02	7.35 ^a ±0.03	62.37 ^c ±0.1	5.10 ^e ±0.02	Bdl	Bdl	Bdl
GRT	5.17 ^e ±0.01	2.62 ^d ±0.04	68.19 ^b ±0.01	12.25 ^b ±0.04	Bdl	Bdl	Bdl

LPT	8.02 ^b ±0.04	4.31 ^c ±0.04	56.01 ^d ±0.1	8.78 ^c ±0.02	Bdl	Bdl	Bdl
LEM	28.31 ^a ±0.03	2.02 ^e ±0.02	85.96 ^a ±0.08	18.31 ^a ±0.03	Bdl	Bdl	Bdl
LSD (p=0.05)	0.02933	0.04506	0.09597	0.03194	Bdl	Bdl	Bdl

(±) standard deviation, *mean of duplicate analysis, mean scores with difference superscript letter across they are significantly different

Key:

AMT = anti-malaria tea

SLM = slimming tea

GRT =green tea

LPT = Lipton tea

LEM = lemongrass tea

BLD = below detectable limit

3. 3. Anti-nutrient content of different tea brands

The present study on tea brands is presented in table 3, compared with LEM (control) showed that all other teas brands had traces of alkaloid at various values ranging from GRT (0.15), AMT (0.08), LPT(0.03), SLM (0.01) and LEM (0.00), Phytate was not detected at all in GRT and was discovered in traces the other tea brands compare with LEM ranging from LEM (0.28), AMT (0.08), LPT (0.06), and SLM (0.03) respectively. Oxalate was also not detected in GRT, but was available in traces in the other tea brands, ranging in the following other LEM (control) (0.25), SLM (0.07), AMT (0.05), and LPT (0.02) respectively.

Table 3. Anti–nutrient content of tea brands

Tea brands	Alkaloid	Phytate	Oxalate
AMT	0.08 ^b ±0.00	0.08 ^b ±0.00	0.05 ^c ±0.00
SLM	0.01 ^d ±0.00	0.03 ^d ±0.00	0.07 ^b ±0.00
GRT	0.15 ^a ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00
LPT	0.03 ^c ±0.00	0.06 ^c ±0.00	0.02 ^d ±0.00
LEM(CONTROL)	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.28 ^a ±0.00	0.25 ^a ±0.00
LSD (p=0.05)	0.00265	0.00259	0.00305

(±) standard deviation, *mean of duplicate analysis, mean scores with difference subscripts letter across, they are significantly different.

Key

AMT = anti-malaria tea

SLM = slimming tea

GRT = green tea

LPT = Lipton tea
 LEM = lemongrass tea

3. 4. Sensory evaluation of the tea brands

The present study of the sensory attributes of tea brands are presented in table 4.4 below. The highest (7.50) color scores was sample LPT (lipton) while the lowest (5.75) color scores were assigned to sample LEM (lemon grass). With highest (7.45) flavor scores was assigned to sample LPT (Lipton) while lowest (5.60) flavor scores were assigned to sample GRT (green tea) and sample AMT (Anti-Malaria tea) (5.60), the result which revealed significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among different tea samples. The average taste scores of tea samples ranged from 6.75-4.95 with highest (6.75) taste scores assigned to sample LPT (Lipton) while lowest (4.95) taste scores were observed in sample AMT (Anti-malaria tea), the result which revealed significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among different tea samples. The average taste scores of tea samples ranged from 6.60-5.30 with highest (6.75) taste scores assigned to sample LPT (Lipton) while lowest (4.95) taste scores were observed in sample AMT (Anti-malaria tea).

Table 4. Organoleptic properties of different tea brands

Tea brands	Colour	Flavour	Taste	Mouth feel	Overall Acceptability
LPT	7.50 ^a ±1.46	7.45 ^a ±1.57	6.75 ^a ±1.44	6.60 ^a ±1.50	8.00 ^a ±1.07
LEM(CONTROL)	5.75 ^b ±1.48	5.95 ^b ±1.87	5.95 ^{ab} ±1.53	6.15 ^{ab} ±1.30	6.50 ^b ±1.31
SLM	6.40 ^{ab} ±1.23	6.00 ^b ±1.48	5.45 ^b ±1.39	6.00 ^{ab} ±1.07	6.00 ^b ±1.07
GRT	6.40 ^{ab} ±1.60	5.60 ^b ±1.60	5.60 ^a ±1.46	5.55 ^a ±1.53	5.75 ^b ±1.40
AMT	6.55 ^{ab} ±1.53	5.60 ^b ±1.14	4.95 ^b ±1.31	5.30 ^b ±1.41	5.75 ^b ±1.40
LSD ($p=0.05$)	0.46487	0.49151	0.45352	0.43589	0.40066

(±) standard deviation, *mean of duplicate analysis, mean scores with difference subscripts letter across, they are significantly different.

Key

AMT = anti-malaria tea

SLM = slimming tea

GRT = green tea

LPT = Lipton tea

LEM = lemongrass

4. DISCUSSION

The relatively low fat content in lemon grass makes it a better tea compared with the other brand of teas in this study (Akande *et al.*, 2012). The significant difference in the comparative

proximate compositions of these tea products, showed that each of the tea possess relative advantage over one another with the Lemon grass being close to the perfect tea. Other heavy metals which were not detectable made the products safe for consumption. Zinc in lemon grass helps boost the immune system and act as antioxidants also (Ferguson *et al.*, 1993). The high content of potassium in lemon grass LEM (control) helps in regulating blood pressure (Victor, 2014). According to Asaolu *et al.*, (2009), analysed the phytochemicals constituents of lemon grass and discovered it contained alkaloid. This was in conformity with Omotade (2009) who discovered oxalate and phytate in traces in his work.

Color: The amino acids in tea have a significant role in color production which may be oxidized by catechins resulting in tea liquor color (Ying *et al.*, 2005; Thippeswamy *et al.*, 2006). In addition to this, other tea components such as thearubigins and theaflavins are also reported to affect the sensory characteristics of the tea especially brightness of tea color (Owuor and Obanda 2001).

Flavor: the result which indicated significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among different tea samples. The difference in flavor score of tea samples may also be due to variations in thearubigins, catechin compounds among green (Khokhar and Magnusdottir, 2002). The results obtained from the present study are in line with previous study of Owuor and Obanda (2001) who observed better flavor scores in commercial tea.

Taste: The quality of tea is strongly associated with the amount of thearubigins, theaflavins, amino acids, and catechins also have a significant contribution in the sensory characteristics of tea (Kato *et al.*, 2008).

Overall acceptability: The results of present study are in line with previous results of Owuor and Obanda (2001) who observed better sensory quality of tea samples having high quality of raw material with maximum amounts of chemical and volatile components used during processing.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

At the end of this research, it can be concluded that the four tea brands evaluated in this study are nutritionally valuable, including the natural extract of lemon grass which contains zinc, which helps boost the immune system and acts as an antioxidant that protects the body. The content of this tea brands and lemon grass are also safe.

This result also showed that Lipton tea (LPT) performed best (8.0) in general acceptability while Green tea (GRT) (5.75) and Anti-malaria tea (AMT) performed poorly (5.75), and that while a regular LEM drinker would be consuming Oxalate every day, the level is modest when compared to the amount gotten from other common foods, it again showed that consumption of tea also provides the body with carbohydrate and less protein and fat.

Based on the findings of this study, the recommendations are made:

- 1) The Nutritional and Therapeutic properties of the tea brands and lemon grass could be linked with their rich content of phytochemicals content.
- 2) Nutritionist and dietitians should always encourage their patient to take tea, most especially lemon grass since it contains zinc and potassium.

- 3) A further research can be carried out on how to produce lemon grass in tea bags, so as to help the individuals who may wish to consume it, but do not have the energy to boil before drinking
- 4) Finally, further studies should be carried out on the general acceptability of lemon grass when Milk is added to it.

References

- [1] AOAC (2000). Official methods of Analysis of Association of Analytical Chemists. *International* 17th ed. Horowitz Maryland.200; 1: 12-20.
- [2] Akande, I. S. I., Samuel, T. A., Agbazue, U. and Olowolagba, B. L. (2012). Comparative proximate analysis of ethanolic and water extracts of *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemon grass) and four tea brands. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences* vol 22: 3-4
- [3] Bender, D.A. (2003). Benders' Dictionary of Nutrition and Food Technology, 7th Edition, CRC Press.
- [4] Byun, J.O. and Han, J.S. (2004). A study perception and actual status of utilization for green tea. *Korean Journal of Food Culture* 18: 184-192
- [5] Enyoh C. E., Ihenetu S.C. and Enyoh E.C. (2019). Proximate and Mineral Composition of *Sesamum Indicum* L. Seed. *Medicinal & Analytical Chemistry International Journal*, 3(4): 1-5.
- [6] Enyoh, C.E., Verla, A.W., Verla, E.N. and Enyoh E.C. (2020). Effect of Macro- and Micro-Plastics in Soil on Quantitative Phytochemicals in Different Part of Juvenile Lime Tree (*Citrus aurantium*). *Int J Environ Res* 14, 705–726
- [7] A. Ferguson, E.L., Gibson, R.S., Opare-Obisan, C., Osei-Opare, F., Stephen, A.M, Lehrfield, J. and Thompson, L.U. (1993). The Zinc, calcium, copper, manganese, Non-starch, Polysaccharide and phytate content of seventy eight locally grown and prepared African Foods. *The Journal of Food Composition and Analysis* 6: 87-89
- [8] Figueirinha, A., Paranhos, A., Perez-Alonso, J.J., Santos-Buelga, C. and Batista, M.A. (2008). *Cymbopogon citratus* leaves: Characterization of flavonoids by HPLC–PDA–ESI/MS/MS and an approach to their potential as a source of bioactive polyphenols. *Journal of Food Chemistry* 110 (3): 718-728
- [9] Hakim, I.A., Weisgerber, U.M., Harris, R.B., Balentine, D., van-Mierlo, C.A.J. and Paetau-Robinson, I. (2000). Preparation, composition and consumption patterns of tea-based beverages in Arizona. *Nutrition Research* 20 (12): 1715-1724
- [10] Hara, Y., Luo, S., Wickremasinghe, R.L. and Yamanishi, T. (2007). Special issue on tea. *Food Reviews International* 11: 371-542
- [11] Ihekoronye, A.Y. and Ngoddy, P.O. (1985). Integrated food science and technology for the tropics. Macmillian publishers, London, pp 202-124

- [12] Kato, A., Y. Minoshima, J., Yamamoto, I. K. Adachi, A.A. Watson and R.J. Nash. (2008). Protective effects of dietary chamomile tea on diabetic complications. *J. Agric. Food Chem*, 56(17): 8206-8211
- [13] Khokhar, S. and Magnusdottir, S.G.M. (2002) .Total phenol, catechin, and caffeine contents of teas commonly consumed in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry*50: 565-570
- [14] Kirk, R.S. and Sawyer, R. (1999). Pearson's Composition and Analysis of Foods (9th Ed) Longman Singapore Publishers; Singapore. 356-362
- [15] Larmond, E. (1977). Laboratory methods for sensory evaluation of food. Res Branch, Canada Dept. of Agric. Canada.
- [16] Olaniyi, A.A., Sofowora, E.A. and Oguntimenin, B.O. (2000). Phytochemical investigation of some Nigerian plants used against fevers. II *Cymbopogon citratus*. *Planta Medica* 28: 186-189
- [17] Omotade I. Oloyede (2009). Chemical profile and antimicrobial activity of *Cymbopogon citratus* leaves. *Journal of Natural Products* 2, 98-103
- [18] Owusu, E. and Odamtten, G.T. (1999). Quality of Ghana herbal tea: microflora and control measures. *Journal of the Ghana Science Association* 1 (3): 84-99
- [19] Owuor, P.O. and M. Obanda. 2001. Comparative responses in plain black tea quality parameters of different tea clones to fermentation temperature and duration. *Food Chemistry* 72(3): 319-327
- [20] Schmidt M., Schmitz H.J., Baumgart, A., Guedon, D., Netsch, M.I. and Kreuter, M.H. (2005). Toxicity of green tea extracts and their constituents in rat hepatocytes in primary culture. *Food Chemistry Toxicology* 43: 307-314
- [21] Thippeswamy, R., Gouda, K. G. M., Rao, D. H., Martin, A. and Gowda, L. W. (2006). Determination of theanine in commercial tea by liquid chromatography with fluorescence and diode array ultraviolet detection. *J. Agric. Food Chem*. 54(19): 7014-7019
- [22] Ying, Y., Ho, J. W., Chen, Z. Y. and Wang, J. (2005). Analysis of theanine in tea leaves by HPLC with fluorescence detection. *J. Liquid Chromat. Rel. Technol*. 28(5): 727-737